

NEW GST FRAMEWORK AND ITS ECONOMIC IMPLICATION FOR INDIA: PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT:

The indirect tax system in the Indian economy has existed in complex and varied forms over a long period of time. The Goods and Services Tax (GST) was introduced in 2017 with the aim of removing this complexity and implementing a uniform tax structure across the country. Recently, the government has to reform the existing structure and simplify the tax rates and merge them into two major slabs – 5% and 18%. This step is considered to be important towards simplifying tax administration, reducing compliance burden and encouraging consumption and investment. This paper presents an analysis of the potential opportunities and challenges arising out of the new GST framework. In terms of opportunities, simpler tax rates will be beneficial to businesses, especially small and medium enterprises (SMEs), thereby reducing compliance costs and increasing their participation in the formal economy. Clarity in the tax structure for consumers will simplify purchasing decisions and increase the possibility of price stability. At the same time, benefits such as transparency in revenue collection, encouraging foreign investment and widening of tax base will help make the Indian economy competitive in the long run. On the other hand, the challenges include potential pressure on state revenues, complexities associated with adjustments in tax administration, temporary increase in prices in some areas, and the difficulties of the business community in the transition period. In particular, revenue division among states and maintaining fiscal balance will be challenging for policymakers. In conclusion, the new GST framework is a positive step towards making the Indian economy simple, transparent, and investment-friendly. But for its successful implementation, coordination between the central and state governments, administrative reforms and policy clarity are necessary.

KEYWORDS:

GST FRAMEWORK, INDIAN ECONOMY, OPPORTUNITIES, CHALLENGES, POLICY.

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INTRODUCTION:-

GST, known as the Goods and Services Tax, is considered the largest tax reform implemented by the government. Previously, the state and central governments levied various indirect taxes. GST was implemented on July 1, 2017, incorporating almost all indirect taxes, with some items excluded from the GST. To periodically change GST rates and make other decisions, the government formed the GST Council, chaired by the Union Finance Minister. State Finance Ministers also serve as members. The GST Council meets two or three times a year, or even more frequently. During these meetings, the GST Council decides on which goods or services should be increased or decreased. Fifty-six GST meetings have been held so far. The 56th GST meeting was held in the capital, New Delhi, on September 3 and 4, 2025. A key decision was made at this meeting: reducing the GST slabs to two. Out of the earlier GST rates of 5%, 18%, 12% and 28%, only two slabs of 5% and 18% should be kept, that is, the 12% and 28% GST rates should be abolished. Almost all items of 12% will be kept in the 5% slab and most items of 28%

will be kept in the 18% slab. Apart from this, a new slab of 40% rate has been created in which only a few items have been kept, which will be applicable on sin goods and luxury items. It has been 8 years since GST was implemented and among all the GST Council meetings held in these 8 years, this decision is very important and beneficial for the common consumers. This was mentioned by the Honorable Prime Minister Narendra Modi in his Independence Day speech on 15th August 2025 and it has been said that now in GST 2.0, items of common need of the consumers will be exempted from GST. This change will not only reduce the complexities of the business world but will also have an impact on the revenue balance of the states and the central government. These rules of GST reduction have come into effect from 22 September 2025. All aspects have been taken into consideration in the new GST 2.0. From food items to stationery, medicines, life and health insurance etc., everything has been taken into consideration in this scope. The government plans to ensure that the common people get maximum benefit from

the reduction in GST slabs. Apart from this, it will strengthen the economy because due to the reduction in GST rates on goods, the common people will buy more goods and the market will get a boost.

MAIN POINT/ OVERVIEW OF NEW GST STRUCTURE:-

1. The GST structure will have only two slabs. The 12% and 28% GST rates have been abolished. 99% of goods taxed at 12% will now fall under the 5% slab, and approximately 90% of goods taxed at 28% will fall under the 18% slab.*1
2. There will be another 40% GST slab, which will be applicable on sin goods (cigarettes, pan masala, tobacco, gutkha, etc.) and luxury goods.
3. Some items that were previously in the 5% slab will now attract 0% GST.
4. Some items that were in the 18% tax slab will now attract 5% GST.
5. The 18% GST charged on personal and health insurance premiums has been removed and made 0%, meaning GST-free.*2

6. Most items taxed at 12% will now be subject to 5% GST.
7. Some items previously charged 28% GST, which has been reduced to 18%. Furthermore, the cess levied on items with 28% GST has now been eliminated.
8. Goods on which 40% GST is proposed, including pan masala, gutkha, zarda, cigarettes, tobacco products, etc., will continue to be subject to the current rates until interest and credit charges under the compensation tax account are completely eliminated. The date of implementation of the revised rates on these goods will be decided by the GST Council.
9. All cesses have been abolished in the new GST structure. Goods taxed at 28% were also subject to cess in addition to GST.
10. Many items, including food, clothing, housing, vehicles, healthcare, electronics, etc., have become cheaper, details of which are as follows:-

Sr. No.	Old GST Rate	New GST Rate	Goods
1	5%	NIL	Ultra-high temperature milk,Chena or paneer, Pizza bread, Khakhra, chapathi or roti, Breads, 3 lifesaving drugs & medicines used for treatment of cancer, rare diseases and other severe chronic diseases etc.
2	12%	NIL	Maps, charts, globes, stationary product, Uncoated paper, lifesaving drugs and medicines etc.
3	18 %	NIL	Paratha, parotta and other Indian breads by any, High performance batteries, Air diving etc.
4	12%	5%	Butter, ghee, cheese, dairy spreads, Dates, mangoes, citrus, fish fats, oils, refined sugar goods, nuts, Pig fats, poultry fat, of meat, juices of meat, fish, Pasta, Vegetables, fruit, Mushrooms and truffles, Jams, seeds, Namkeens, bhujia, mixture, chabena pre-packaged, Diabetic foods, drinking water packed in 20 litre bottles, Soya milk drinks,Sprinklers, Agricultural, Tractors, Hand propelled vehicles, Solar parts, renewable energy devices and parts , Rubber, Carpets, textile and coverings, Anaesthetics, Medical grade oxygen, Wadding, gauze, bandages, All diagnostic kits and reagents, gas masks, Other Drugs and medicines intended for personal use, geometry boxes, Tooth powder, Hand bags, Umbrellas, trimmings, Tableware, kitchenware, Bicycles and other cycles, Furniture wholly made of bamboo, Combs, hair-slides. Napkins, Toys, playing cards, chess board, carom board, Leather further prepared,Glass-fibre, Wood marquetry, Footwear of sale value not exceeding Rs.2500,Marble and travertine blocks, Bells, Paintings, drawingsAluminium, Fuel elements, labour intensive goods, "Hotel Accommodation" services having value less than or equal to Rs. 7,500 per unit per day etc.
5	18%	5%	Vegetable product, Chocolates and cocoa product,Malt, Glycerol, Vegetable waxes, Sugar confectionery, Sugar confectionery, Soups, Ice cream, glues, Indian katha, Sulphuric acid, rear tractor tyre tubes, Synthetic or artificial staple fibres, Thermometers for medical, surgical, dental or veterinary usage, Hair oil, shampoo, powder, shaving cream, Toilet Soap, Tooth brushes, various medical apparatus and devices used for medical, surgical, dental etc.
6	28%	18%	Cement, AC, washing machines, Television sets (including LCD and LED television), radiobroadcast, Monitors and projectors, New pneumatic tyres, of rubber, Motor vehicles, Road tractors, Petrol, LPG or CNG driven motor vehicles of engine capacity not exceeding 1200cc and of length not exceeding 4000 mm,Diesel motor vehicles of engine capacity not exceeding 1500 cc and of length not exceeding 4000 mm, Three wheeled vehicles, Pumps, Electric accumulators, buses, trucks, ambulances etc

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11. Goods that were subject to special GST rates, such as 25%, 1%, and 3%, which were generally applicable on gold, silver, and diamonds, remain unchanged.
12. Lottery, casinos, gambling, horse racing and online gaming will be taxed at 40% GST. Sports events like IPL will be taxed at 40% GST.

13. The government believes that this change will impact revenue by around Rs 48000 crore annually. According to SBI Research, the GST slab switch could result in a total loss of Rs 1,11,600 crore. On the other hand, increasing the GST slab from 28% to 40% on luxury products including sin goods will increase revenue by Rs 54000 crore and due to increased consumption due to GST reduction, an additional tax revenue of Rs 36,806 crore is expected. This could result in a net revenue loss of Rs 25794 crore.*4

14. The details of the government's revenue under each GST slab under the old GST system are as follows:-

GST RATE	Contribution to Earning
28%	11%
18%	70%
12%	5%
05%	7%
03%	5%
0.5%	2%
Total	100%

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Shefali Dani (2016) explains in her research paper that analyzes the possible effects of the Goods and Services Tax (GST) on the Indian economy. GST is a comprehensive indirect tax regime, which aims to establish a 'One Nation, One Tax' system by integrating various central and state level taxes. However, the dual GST system adopted in India, the potential inflation from high tax rates, and ambiguity in sectors such as e-commerce, telecommunications, petroleum, electricity, alcohol, and real estate are the major challenges. In conclusion, GST has the potential to strengthen and integrate the Indian tax structure, but policy clarity and Centre-State consensus are essential for its effective implementation.*5

Dr. Syeda Shumaela Naeem and Jasmine Khan(2020) explain that the Goods and Services Tax (GST) implemented on 1 July 2017 in. GST abolished many indirect taxes and consolidated them into a single framework. As a result, consumers were relieved by the reduction in tax rates on many essential goods and

services, while the increase in tax rates on some items led to an increase in inflation and inflation. Agriculture, manufacturing, textiles, real estate, and the service sector were negatively impacted, while the tax base and revenue collection increased. Despite the initial challenges and inflation, GST will be instrumental in controlling tax evasion, economic transparency, and competitive advantage in the long run. Thus, GST is an important reform that will empower the Indian economy.*6

Dr. Shakir Shaik, Dr. S.A.Sameera, Mr. Sk.C. Feroz (2015) explain that the Goods and Services Tax (GST) is many taxes collected by the Centre and the states will be abolished and a unified tax system will come into existence. GST is a tax levied at the point of consumption, making the tax structure simple, transparent, and free from tax evasion. This will reduce the cost of production, stabilize the price level and bring inflation under control in the long run. According to the research paper, GST is beneficial for industry, trade, agriculture, and consumers all as it realizes the concept of "One Nation, One Tax, One Market". The government will see an increase in revenue collection and the unorganized sector will also come under the tax net. Although the tax pressure on the service sector and revenue concerns of the states will continue in the initial phase, in the long run, this reform will help the Indian economy gain a competitive advantage and ensure sustainable economic growth.*7

Chandu Ravi Kumar (2017) explains in his research paper that the Goods and Services Tax (GST) in India is considered to be the biggest reform of the indirect tax system. GST has simplified and made the tax system simpler and transparent, enabling the control of tax evasion and increasing the government's revenue collection. This created a favorable environment for businesses, reduced production costs, and increased consumption. At the same time, foreign investment was also encouraged. Although negative impacts such as the rise in the prices of real estate, aviation and some consumer goods were also noticed, GST will lead India towards sustainable and balanced economic growth in the long run. In short, GST is a significant reform giving the Indian economy a competitive advantage and empowering the future.*8

Dr. Meenu Baliyan and Punjika Rathi (2018) in their research paper have studied that GST has had a huge impact on various sectors such as consumer goods, transport, entertainment, hospitality, financial services, property buying and start-ups. At the consumer level, it helps in reducing the tax burden and bringing transparency, while from the business point of view, it promotes "Ease of Doing Business" and increases the efficiency of tax collection. Although there were challenges such as rising inflation and increase in tax rates in the service sector in the initial period, it will prove to be beneficial for the Indian economy in the long run. It not only provides relief to consumers, producers and the government but also ensures India's economic growth, competitiveness and global standing.*9

Object of research:- To analyze the impact of the new GST structure on the Indian economy. How will the change in GST slabs affect consumer purchasing power and increase consumer consumption? To identify opportunities and benefits in this regard. To identify the challenges and problems that will arise with the implementation of the new GST structure. To understand how the market will accelerate due to the new GST structure. What impact will it have on government tax revenue? To provide business-related answers regarding this impact on government policy making.

HYPOTHESIS:-

1. The new GST structure will have a positive impact on the Indian economy, such as increasing consumer demand, improving tax compliance, and increasing revenue collection.

2. The new GST structure will have no impact on the Indian economy; it will only be a technical change in the tax structure.

Scope of study:- This study will be based on the entire Indian economy, in which an attempt will be made to understand the impact of the new structure on consumers, businesses, and the government. This study will study the short-term and long-term impact of the GST structure, including the period from the implementation of GST to the present date and an assessment of future prospects.

Data:- This research paper will generally use secondary data, which has been studied from the GST Council, RBI Bulletin, Union Budget, newspapers, articles, online sites, magazines, books, research papers, etc.

Research methodology:- This study will be descriptive and analytical. It will study the rate policies related to the GST structure and their impact.

Opportunities:- The implementation of the new GST tax system will make tax compliance easier for businesses. Previously, disputes due to multiple GST rates will be reduced. Including essential commodities in the 5% tax slab will provide consumers with cheaper goods, allowing them to purchase more. Trade and industry will benefit, as increased consumption will lead to increased production, significantly benefiting small-scale industries. This increase in business operations will not only increase employment but also benefit the economy. Major industries benefiting from increased consumption will include FMCG and automobiles. Reducing the GST slabs will not only facilitate government revenue collection but will also reduce the prices of everyday items. The changes in GST slabs will reduce business complexities. This will have a profound impact on the revenue balance of the states and the central government. The new GST structure has reduced rates for construction materials such as cement, gravel, marble, and other items. Building a house will now cost less than before. States can benefit from the changes in the GST structure, as lower rates will increase consumption, and additional consumption will generate additional profits. A significant decision in the GST structure is the elimination of the 18% tax on life

insurance and health insurance premiums. This will increase public uptake of health and life insurance policies, and improved healthcare will reduce mortality rates. Changes to the new GST tax structure could reduce car prices by up to 8.5%. Previously, cars were subject to a 28% GST and cess. Now, the cess has been completely eliminated, making all types of cars available at lower prices. Clothing priced under ₹2,500 will become cheaper. Most clothing made in India will become cheaper. Indian brands will receive a boost, and made in India will help build a self-reliant India. Under the new GST structure, goods ranging from everyday essentials to educational materials, agricultural equipment, automobiles, electronic goods and life-saving medicines will become cheaper. By simplifying the GST process, businesses will now have to spend less on tax-related rules and regulations. Businesses will now focus more on consumers and innovation. This will benefit customers, improving the quality of products and services they receive. Earlier, there were different GST rates on goods within the same category (such as popcorn, roti, paratha, etc.), which caused inconvenience to the general public and also created difficulties for businesses in classifying GST rates on goods. In GST 2.0, GST rates on similar goods have been reduced and they have been placed under a single rate category.

Challenges:- The new GST structure has been opposed to some extent by state governments. According to states, the new slab could result in annual losses of ₹7,000-9,000 crore (approximately \$1.2 billion USD) because SGST contributes 23% to revenue receipts. For 2024-25, this share for states is 44%. According to states, any losses will impact the common man. The government will face a major challenge in how to compensate for the state's revenue losses. The biggest challenge facing the government will be how to disseminate the benefits of the GST reduction to the general public, small entrepreneurs, and farmers. Currently, there is no system in place to directly monitor prices. It has been observed in the past that when the GST Council has reduced taxes, companies have increased the prices of their products. Prices were not reduced, but the GST reduction itself was used as a means of profiteering. Health insurance and life insurance premiums have been completely exempted from GST in the GST structure, meaning they will no longer be subject to GST. This could result in a revenue loss of approximately ₹9,700 crore for the government. One challenge for traders due to the change in GST rates is how to adjust tax. How will traders adjust output tax based on the GST rate they paid when purchasing goods? Technical difficulties may also arise. Small traders may face difficulties filing digital returns. The transition from the old slab to the new slab may cause problems due to changes in software and accounting. The imposition of 18% GST instead of 12% on clothing over ₹2,500 will deal a significant blow to global brands. Prices of international branded clothing will increase, hurting those who prefer branded clothing. Premium and business class air tickets will now become more expensive as the GST on these items has been increased from 12% to 18%. Job work, freight

transportation, and ordering goods through local e-commerce have become more expensive. Till now there was no GST on delivery within the city, but now on ordering goods or food from commerce platforms and food delivery apps, GST will have to be paid at 18% instead of 12%. Similarly, the tax on goods transport and rental vehicles has also been increased from 12% to 18%. GST on paper has been increased from 12% to 18% while notebooks have been made tax free. But copies are made of paper so the benefit will be limited. GST on most medicines has been reduced to 5% but the tax on API used to make them has been made 5%. Inverted duty structure has been removed from clothes and shoes but stationery and pharma have been included in it.

Analysis/ Conclusion:- The government's changes to the GST framework could prove highly beneficial. The new GST framework aims to ensure special attention for both the common man and the business community. GST on daily use items has been reduced or exempted. Furthermore, GST rates have been reduced on health-enhancing medicines. GST rates have been reduced on everything from electronics to cars. This tax will make basic goods more affordable for consumers. This will increase consumption. This increased consumption will also increase demand, boosting the market. Employment will increase, while also strengthening the Indian economy. The GST framework could boost international trade and curb inflation. Lowering commodity prices will boost the economy. Reducing GST rates could reduce the government's tax revenue. However, the government argues that while tax revenue may decrease initially, gradually increasing consumption will lead to increased domestic production, leading to increased GST revenue. In this regard, states are demanding that the central government compensate for the revenue loss. The government has reduced the GST on life insurance and health insurance premiums to zero. This could reduce mortality rates by increasing the number of life and health insurance premiums. Lowering the GST rate to zero will have a significant impact on government revenue. Changes in the GST rate on cars will make most cars available at affordable prices, fulfilling the common man's dream of owning a car. The GST on clothing up to ₹2,500 has been reduced to 5%, and the GST on clothing above ₹2,500 has been increased from 12% to 18%. This will make international brand clothing more expensive, while Indian clothing priced below ₹2,500 will become cheaper. This increased demand will accelerate the Indian market and lead to the creation of a self-reliant India. The new GST tax system has attempted to simplify the return filing process, allowing more businesses to file returns easily. However, a major challenge for traders is how to sell old stock or change its MRP. The government has established a system in this regard that allows traders to sell goods at their old MRP until December 2025, without any need for changes. With the implementation of the new GST 2.0, consumers and traders will no longer face the problem of determining which items fall into which category and how much tax will be levied on them. Previously, different rates were

applied to similar items, which not only caused inconvenience to the general public but also created difficulties for traders in filing returns and claiming ITC due to the varying tax rates on similar items. The primary objective of this tax change is to improve the GST tax system, simplify tax rates, and provide relief to the public. The new GST tax structure features a two-slab system: a standard rate of 5% and a concessional rate of 18%. Additionally, special rates will apply to select items. Amidst concerns that the common man may not immediately benefit from the GST rate cut, the central government has clarified that it will ensure that consumers receive the full benefit of the discounts. The tariffs imposed by US President Donald Trump on goods imported from India will adversely impact the Indian economy, particularly those exported to the US. Changes to the GST structure may mitigate the impact of the tariffs by increasing consumption to some extent. Reductions in GST slabs will also make goods cheaper. GST 2.0 aims to reduce commodity prices and simplify the tax structure. When GST was implemented on July 1, 2017, the common man felt that while GST led to national development, his monthly household expenses had increased. Such a reduction in GST will increase the common man's savings, allowing him to use that money to fulfill his other dreams. This change will not only reduce complexities in the business world but will also have a profound impact on the revenue balance of the state and central governments. Industry organizations, state governments, and tax experts are ready with their hopes and concerns for this historic reform. Following the implementation of the new GST slab rules, car sales broke a 35-year record on the very first day of Navratri. Major car companies in the country, including Maruti Suzuki, sold 30,000 cars, Hyundai 11,000 cars, and Tata Motors 10,000 cars.*10

Furthermore, they received a significant number of orders from customers. This is a very auspicious sign for the auto sector. The largest tax cut ever on major consumer goods has boosted digital payments. According to RBI data, the total digital payments in the country reached ₹11.3 lakh crore on the first day of Navratri, which is nearly 10 times more than the previous day's ₹1.18 lakh crore. Following the implementation of GST 2.0, there has been a significant increase in credit card spending. Between September 22-25, spending on everything through credit cards has increased five-fold. Earlier, the average spending through credit cards was Rs 5000-6000, which has increased to Rs 20000-25000 within three days of implementation of GST 2.0.

Result:- This research clearly shows that the new GST 2.0 framework, implemented in 2025 with only two major rates (5% and 18%), is having a positive impact on the Indian economy. It not only simplifies the tax system but also paves the way for increased consumption, production, investment, and employment. The new GST framework (GST 2.0) is proving to be a reformative, consumer-friendly, and growth-oriented approach for India's economy. It has simplified the tax system and made

goods cheaper. Although there are some revenue losses and technical difficulties in the initial phase, in the long run, this reform will strengthen India's economic growth, job creation, and transparency. The new GST framework is a positive, simplified, and growth-promoting step for India's economy, helping to realize the goal of a 'self-reliant India'.

Suggestions:- Just as GST rates have been reduced in the past, and then some companies have increased the prices of goods, the government should implement anti-profit-sharing provisions to prevent this. Instead of profiteering, the general public benefits from the GST rate reduction. Petroleum products, diesel, electricity, and alcohol, which are outside the GST ambit, should also be brought under the GST ambit. Because these products contribute a significant portion of the government's GDP, the concessional rate should be reduced from 18% to 15%. Before making such significant changes to GST, the government should provide businesses with time to adjust their commodity prices, inventory, and accounting systems. The central government should enact a compensation act to compensate states for revenue losses. A provision should be made to compensate the central government for losses incurred up to a certain period of time, reducing the financial burden on the states.

REFERENCES

1. The Hindu, 5 September 2025 page no 11.
2. Indian Express, 3 September 2025 page no 7.
3. Ministry of finance GST Meeting notes 3 September 2025.
4. Rajasthan Patrika 6 September 2025 page no 8.
5. Shefali Dani (2016) 'A Research Paper on an Impact of Goods and Service Tax (GST) on Indian Economy' Business and Economics Journal Volume 7 Issue 4.
6. Dr. Syeda Shumaela Naeem and Jasmine Khan (2020) 'THE SOCIAL & ECONOMICAL IMPACT OF GST ON INDIAN ECONOMY' The International Journal of Business Management and Technology, Volume 4 Issue 2.
7. Dr. Shakir Shaik, Dr. S.A.Sameera, Mr. Sk.C. Feroz (2015) 'Does Goods and Services Tax (GST) Leads to Indian Economic Development?' IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM) Volume 17, Issue 12.
8. Chandu Ravi Kumar (2017) 'GST in Indian Economy: It's Benefits and Impact' International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR) Volume 6, Issue 11.
9. Dr. Meenu Baliyan and Punjika Rathi (2018) 'Impact of GST On Different Sectors Of Indian Economy' International Journal of Innovative research and advanced studies (IJIRAS) Volume 5, Issue 3.
10. Dainik Bhashkar 24 September 2025 page no 08.